

Acid Hydrolysis of Propionamide*

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Kinetics of acid hydrolysis of propionamide has been investigated in 0.05 to 7 M perchloric acid at 70°. The rate constants increase with an increase in acid concentration and attains optimum value in 3 M acid. Arrhenius parameters, kinetic order and the ionic strength data support a bimolecular nucleophilic attack of water on the conjugate acid species of propionamide. The variation of reaction rate with acid concentration is explained in terms of a two parameter equation which takes into account the relative amounts of free and protonated substrate and a kinetic salt effect and the water activity raised to some power.

It has long been established that the acid hydrolysis of the amides¹ usually proceeds by the bimolecular mechanism, A_{AC} ². Further, these exhibit rate maxima, which have generally been considered to arise because, once the amide is fully protonated a further increase in acid concentration merely decreases the water activity². We have given in our previous papers a different explanation^{3,6} for the maxima which includes the negative ionic strength effect also. The study of the propionamide was undertaken to see the validity of the new equation earlier proposed^{3,6}.

Reagents : Propionamide (m.p. 79°) was prepared by the reaction of urea and propionic acid⁴. The constant ionic strengths were maintained using mixtures of HClO₄ and NaClO₄. The hydrolysis was followed by Sorenson's formal titration method as described previously^{3,5}.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

First order rate constants in amide are independent of its concentration (Table 1). The rate constant increases with the rise in acid concentration and has an optimum rate at 3 M acid. Such maxima were also observed in the hydrolysis of other amides,^{2,3} lactams⁶,

TABLE 1

Effect of varying concentration of the substrate on the hydrolysis of propionamide in perchloric acid at 70°

Amide (M)	HClO (M)	$k \times 10^3$ (min. ⁻¹)
0.05	1.0	14.03
0.10	1.0	13.82
0.15	1.0	14.40

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lactides⁷ and aryl phosphates⁸. The bend may be due to the negative ionic strength⁷ or due to decreasing role of water with the increase in acidity² or due to both.^{3,6} As has been done for the hydrolysis of acetamide³ the rate constants were determined at various acidities by keeping constant ionic strength and the results are shown in Table 2. From the plot of rate coefficients against acidity at different ionic strengths, it can be concluded that (i) at each ionic strength the reaction can be represented by,

$$k = k_{H^+} C_{H^+} \quad \dots (1)$$

where k and k_{H^+} are the observed and specific rate constants. (ii) Since the slopes (k_{H^+}) of the lines decrease with the increase in ionic strength, the reaction exhibits a negative ionic strength effect (Table 2). (iii) The reaction due to neutral species is absent as lines pass through the origin.

TABLE 2

Effect of varying ionic strength on reaction rate at 70°

$\frac{HClO_4}{(M)}$	$\frac{NaClO_4}{(M)}$	Ionic strength (μ)	$k \times 10^3$ min^{-1}	$k_{H^+} \times 10^3$ $M^{-1} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$
0.2	0.8	1.0	3.98	14.0
0.5	0.5	1.0	7.82	
0.8	0.2	1.0	12.10	
1.5	0.5	2.0	20.44	12.0
1.8	0.2	2.0	21.10	
2.0	0.0	2.0	20.80	
2.0	1.0	3.0	19.82	10.0
2.5	0.5	3.0	25.3	
2.5	1.5	4.0	19.19	6.0
3.0	1.0	4.0	18.95	
3.5	0.5	4.0	17.81	

These results are in favour of the reaction via only protonated species, which is subject to negative salt effect. The rate data obey Equation (2).

$$k = 17.78 \times 10^{-3} C_{H^+} e^{-0.1\mu} (a_{H_2O})^n \quad \dots (2)$$

(where a_{H_2O} is activity of water¹⁰ and "n" is the number of water molecules), which is a modified form of the Bronsted-Bjerrum equation applied to the conventional reaction scheme⁹.

where S is an amide and (X^\ddagger) is the transition complex. The values 17.78×10^{-3} litre mole⁻¹ min.⁻¹ and 0.1 in equation (2) are respectively the intercept at zero ionic strength ($k_{H_3O^+}$) and the slope of the linear plot between $\log k_{H^+}$ and μ .

The theoretical rates at different acidities have been calculated using $n = 1$ in Eq. (2) are in agreement up to 4 *M* perchloric acid. Beyond 4 *M* acidity the value of $n = 2$ in Eq. (2) improves the agreement fairly well. The latter view has been supported by the fact that at these high acidities ($> 4 M$) water is required both for solvation and for reaction¹. Values of Arrhenius parameters. E (19.8 K cal/mole), A (1.0×10^{10} min.⁻¹) and ΔS^\ddagger (-19.7 e.u.) are in favour of the bimolecular mechanism as suggested in the scheme.

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